

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15529971

Foreign Economic Policy And Foreign Direct Investment In Nigeria: A Study Of Goodluck Jonathan's Administration, 2010-2015

Godwin, Joyce Okwang; Agary Nwaokoye, Ph.D & Emesiani, Ifeanyi Godspower

**Department of Political Science,
Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

Nigeria foreign economic policy during Jonathan administration focused on the realization of transformation agenda through the attraction of foreign direct investment, to achieve these, the government directed diplomatic missions abroad to focus more on attracting investment to support the domestic programs of government with a view to achieving an enduring legacy of economic prosperity in-line with Jonathan's "transformation agenda". However, the Jonathan administration like any other administration in Nigeria never lack good foreign economic policies, but the problem lies in the implementation to translate the policies into action that will benefit the country's population, the overall inflow of foreign direct investment during the period did not have much impact on the country's domestic industrial capacity, no improvement on industries, infrastructure, manufacturing and agriculture etc. The research addressed some fundamental questions, how did Nigeria foreign economic policy under Goodluck Jonathan's administration engender FDI between 2010-2015? How effective has foreign economic policy been in attracting foreign direct investment during Goodluck Jonathan administration? What are the major impacts of Foreign Economic Policy under the Goodluck Jonathan's administration on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI in Nigeria)? The research reviewed and adopted dependency theory to help explained the research topic, the research adopts qualitative research method, secondary data collection was used, it involves intense library search, textbooks, policy documents, journals, internet materials relevant to the topic. The research discovered that Nigeria foreign economic policy during Jonathan's administration engender foreign direct investment, it was also reviled that foreign economic policy has not been effective in attracting foreign direct investment between the period of 2010-2015, the research further discovered that foreign direct investment has no positive impact on domestic industrial capacity. The study recommended that Nigeria government should further check the actual implementation of foreign economic policy agenda to ensure the basic objectives of foreign direct investment is achieved, FDI implementation should look at domestic interest of economy like agriculture, infrastructure, industries etc. also recommend that rather than depend and canvass for foreign direct investment which is usually attracted at concessionary terms, the government should invest more in the provision of infrastructural facilities to boost domestic economic activities that would create the right economic environment attractive to foreign capital investment without having to depend on what may not have impact on domestic productivity.

Keywords: Foreign Economic Policy, Foreign Direct Investment

INTRODUCTION

The goal of any state in international relations is the achievement of domestic needs and strategic interests, states engage in bilateral or multilateral interactions as a way of acquiring the support and services of other states towards achieving affairs that exists outside their borders. Economic and other strategic interest drives states foreign policy. Heywood, (2007) put it that. Foreign policy is the diverse conceptions as an ideology, a strategy, an even the processes that define international relations. In pursuits of foreign policy, nation-states can go to any length to project and protect their national interest; thus, in interstate relations diplomatic maneuvers, bargaining, negotiations, persuasions, propaganda, moral warfare, blackmail, etcetera are used to achieve state foreign policy goals and objectives. The level of economic development of any country has a crucial role to play in realizing economic foreign policy goals and objectives.

The concept of foreign economic policy signifies the influence of the state on economic relations with foreign countries, in particularly on commodity and services turnover as well as flow of factors of production. Economic foreign policy is thus, connected with the state's competence to make decisions on foreign economic relations (Okolie, 2009). These powers can be more or less extensive due to internal as well as external reasons. In the case of the former, it is the economic model that determines the powers of the state; under liberal economy conditions where individual economic entities play the principal role in economic relations, the scope of the state's powers is narrower; limitation of liberalism being accompanied by growth of the powers of the state. In the case of the latter, where the scope of the state's power is determined by external reasons, an autonomous policy and an agreement policy can be distinguished (Soldaczuk 2001). This implies that the foreign economic policy of a state should be comprehensive, which means it should cover both economic relations with foreign countries and the internal economic relations of a given country.

Several overlapping trends of economic strategies emerged in the history of Nigeria foreign economic policy. Thus: Policy of Dependent Import Substitution Industrialization (DISI), 1960 – 1974; the policy of Regional Economic Integration (REI), 1970 – 1985; and the policy of the establishment of the New International Economic Order (NIEO), 1973 – 1985. It was however the policy of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) introduced by the Ibrahim Babangida administration in 1986 that marked the watershed in Nigeria's foreign economic policy. As pursued in Nigeria, the policy of Structural Adjustment Programme was christened the "new" foreign economic policy in the sense that it represented an attempt for the first time in Nigeria's diplomatic history to consciously and deliberately shift the emphasis in Nigeria's foreign economic policy from political considerations to economic motives. Before 1986, it was an important tradition of Nigeria's foreign economic policy to try to balance what Nigerian policy makers generally regarded as the two imperatives in Nigeria's external relations. These were a leading political role for Nigeria in the international system, especially in the African sub-system and the promotion of Nigeria's economic development objectives. In the third quarter of 1986 however, there emerged signs of a rethink of that policy (Asobie, 1991).

Foreign economic policy of Goodluck Ebele Jonathan Administration could be traced to the National Technical Working Group (NTWG) setup in 2009 while Jonathan was still the Vice President, the NTWG was mandated to review the foreign policy direction of Nigeria up till 2009, the Working Group determined that Nigeria's major focus on the African countries as her core foreign policy direction has not benefit the country well, looking at the current economic realities, recommended that the Nigeria foreign policy should be more on providing solutions to domestic problems rather than carrying the whole Africa continent as core priority. Goodluck Jonathan did not take much to adopt the recommendation when he became the President of the country. This recommendation was adopted when President Jonathan declared that the major objective of foreign policy under his administration was to attract more investments from outside the country as a means of induce positive movements in the domestic economy of Nigeria (Vanguard, 2012). In the words of the then President, because his administration had identified economic growth based on the expansion/development of the knowledge industry, given its impact towards arresting youth unemployment and therefore restiveness among it army of young people, as essential in Nigeria's quest to tackle increasing insecurity within its borders, "Nigeria's foreign policy is now anchored on the

realization of this transformation agenda through the attraction of foreign direct investment. Under the new policy thrust, our diplomatic missions abroad have been directed to focus more on attracting investment to support the domestic programs of government with a view to achieving not only our Vision 20: 2020, but to bequeathing an enduring legacy of economic prosperity” (Vanguard, 2012). President Jonathan in pursuit of the country’s foreign economic policy, made it a point of duty to organize a forum for interacting with Nigerians who were living in any country he visited during his diplomatic visits to redeemed the image and status of Nigerian, to him, Nigerians in the diaspora constituted a resource that the country needed to harness in her bid to engineer national economic development.

In keeping with the administration’s focus of deploying foreign economic policy for solving domestic issues, the GEJ administration insisted on deploying diplomacy for articulating and vigorously marketing the country as an investment destination for businesses. While the government under the leadership of Umaru Musa Yar’Adua had put forward a “seven-point agenda”, GEJ decided to add a personal touch to those objectives and review his plans to “transformation agenda”. The urgent issues under the transformation agenda included, agriculture, the opening of rural areas through infrastructure development, improving the security situation, etc. The government was focused particularly on improving and enhancing business connections with foreign partners as a basis for prosperity and progress (Chidozie, Ibietan & Ujara, 2014). Investors with capital and technical know-how in key areas of Nigeria’s economy with high rates of return on investment, were invited from U.S. to take advantage of the economic foreign policy incentives and invest more in Nigeria, by the year 2015, Nigeria would have witnessed transformation in all sectors to the benefit of not only its citizens, but also those who have an interest in Nigeria, President Jonathan concluded.

Asobie (1991) observed that successive Nigerian governments have demonstrated an appreciation of the linkage between the country’s foreign economic policy and her foreign direct investment but that the way in which this linkage was conceived and the policies deriving there however differed, though not necessarily from regime to regime. Foreign direct investment (FDI) is in many forms and the term is used to refer to different kinds of investment activity. Generally, FDI is a measure of foreign ownership of productive assets, factories, mines and land. It is direct investment into production or business in a country by corporate bodies and citizens from another country. The end of World War II marked a significant watershed in the recognition and use of FDI as a very viable economic growth path, especially for the developing countries, (Lall, 2002). For instance, the contributions of foreign investment to Japan after the World War II and in South Korea after the Korean War are of great importance. In the same vein, Thailand, Singapore, Malaysia, Taiwan, Hong Kong and Indonesia which were once reputed to be economic tigers of Asia owe a significant part of their past successes and much of their current growth largely to heavy inflows of FDI over the years.

In Nigeria, the first FDI effort was by The Royal Niger Company (RNC) which was in the 19th century and under Sir Tubman Goldie arrived on the shores of Nigeria from Great Britain. The commercial and economic conquests of the RNC soon translated into the formal establishment of political control in Nigeria for Great Britain. The same went for other companies like United Trading Company (UTC), United African Company (UAC) - two descendants of the RNC- and others. This development formed the background to the advent and activities of multinational corporations in Nigeria, (Onu, 2012). Nigeria became one of the economies with great demand for goods and services and has attracted many FDI over the years since the discovery of crude oil. According to the World Bank, from 1970 to 1979, Nigeria recorded an average ratio of foreign direct investment net inflow of about 1.579 to GDP while from 1980 to 1989, the average ratio of FDI net inflow to GDP recorded stood at 1.947. Thus, in 1993 and 1994, the country made a remarkable record of 6.3 and 8.28 respectively. Since 1993 and 1994, the record was not an issue to contend with. To the greatest dismay, from 1995 to 2010, FDI, net inflow as % of GDP in Nigeria has not gone beyond 4.0 except in 1996, 1997, 2005 and 2009 the country made a record of 4.51, 4.25, 4.44 and 5.08 respectively. World Bank research contained in global Development Finance 2008 shows that Thailand attracted \$9.6 billion in 2007 while Nigeria attracted just about \$6.03 billion. Total foreign direct investment inflow into Nigeria in 2010 was about \$5.99 billion. The breakdown of the

amount according to the report shows that FDI portion was just 12.2 percent or \$668 million. This represents a 78.1 percent drop from \$3.31 billion in 2009 (Adeleke, Olowe & Fasesin, 2014).

Furthermore, policy makers in developing countries including Nigeria have sought over time to attract more and more FDI in order to accelerate economic growth, job creation and poverty reduction. This is based on the premise that FDI is a way of obtaining capital and technology that is not available in the host country (Olusanya, 2013). For reasons of globalization as well as revolutions in all areas of economic life worldwide, there is no gainsaying the fact that knowledge on the effect of FDI on economic growth, value addition, employment, poverty and such likes in Nigeria needs to be updated. It is for this reason that this study centers on the effect of FDI on economic growth in Nigeria with particular emphasis on aggregate and sectoral implications and performance as regards aggregate production, monetary prices, external shock and others. Summarily, the foreign economic policy aims to deepen the effects of FDI and provide a sense of priority policies and programs which when implemented would transform the Nigerian economy to meet the future needs of the people.

Nigeria is a resource- rich country and its oil and gas sector has attracted much FDI inflows than other sectors. Other major recipients of FDI inflows in Nigeria include banking, manufacturing, construction, and telecommunication sectors (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2018). Despite Nigeria's attractive economy, having the largest market size in Africa, the country could not fully attract FDI inflows needed for economic growth. This may not be unconnected to the fear of risk in investment, political risk, insecurity challenges, policy inconsistencies, etc. (Collier & Hoeffler, 2014). African countries are stock in internal conflict as evidenced by communal, religious, political crises or sectional agitation (Collier 2008). The inflow of foreign direct investment throughout the Jonathan administration from 2010 to 2015 could not guarantee overall stability or growth in the domestic economic activities like industries, agriculture, manufacturing etc, due to the aforementioned challenges expressed in extant literature, the study critically examined foreign economic policy and foreign direct investment of Goodluck Jonathan administration 2010 to 2015. On this note, the study poses the following research questions.

1. How did Nigeria foreign economic policy under Goodluck Jonathan's administration engender FDI between 2010-2015.
2. How effective has foreign economic policy been in attracting foreign direct investment during Goodluck Jonathan administration?
3. What are the major impacts of Foreign Economic Policy under the Goodluck Jonathan's administration on Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Nigeria?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Foreign Economic Policy

The study conceptualized foreign Economic policy as all activities that deals with the state interaction with another state in all economic relations. Such activities may include the trade negotiation, distribution of foreign aid, and the management/regulation of import and export commodities. foreign Economic. policy is very important and central for a country's role within the world economy system and international trade in general. Foreign economic policy is defined by Goldstein and Pevehouse (2011) as the "states competence to make decisions on foreign economic relations". Carlsnaes (2008) approached the definition of foreign economic policy in a more detailed form. He argued that it: consists of those actions which, expressed in the form of explicitly stated goals, commitments and/or directives, and pursued by governmental representatives acting on behalf of their sovereign communities, are directed toward objectives, conditions and actors – both governmental and non-governmental – which they want to affect and which lie beyond their economic territorial legitimacy. This implies that, for countries to relate effectively with one another, foreign economic policy must be well defined, well thought out, and must possess direction.

Hence, Adeniran (1982) infers that foreign economic policy can best be understood through an explanation of what it actually is. Foreign economic policy, according to him consists of three elements. One is the „overall orientation and economic policy intentions“ of a particular country toward another. The second element is the „objective“ that a country seeks to achieve in her economic relations or

economic dealings with other countries. The third element of foreign economic policy is the “means” for achieving that particular goal or objectives. According to (Legg et al, 1971) “economic foreign policy is a set of explicit objectives with regard to the world beyond the borders of a given social unit and a set of strategies and tactics designed to achieve those economic objectives”. This understanding subscribes to the designation of plans and clear cut strategies for actualization of those plans. It is idealist because it fails to take cognizance of the contingencies in the international system in terms of the unpredictability of behaviors of international actors. Another conceptualization of foreign economic policy emerged from the obvious shortcoming of the above view. This view was well articulated by Vital (1968). To him, “foreign economic policy implies rather a field of related but distinct actions and issues in which there neither is nor can be foreign policy”. According to his thesis, the realities of states’ behavior entail decisions and policies being formulated in a disjointed fashion, largely in response to immediate pressures and events, in a number of separate structures and issue areas. Thus, Frankel’s (1964 and 1975) conception of foreign economic policy “as a dynamic process of interaction between the changing domestic demands and the changing external circumstances” is apt in the light of occurrences in contemporary global political order. Ade-Ibijola (2013) simply defined Nigerian foreign economic policy as the driving factor behind Nigeria’s economic interaction with other nations of the world. He further summed it as the declared intentions of a state. This conception of foreign economic policy can simply be reconstructed to read as the declared intentions of a state in economic relation to other states. Foreign economic policy therefore is a product of internal environment and external circumstances. It is concerned with the conducts, actions as well as behaviors of a state towards other states and the economic goals and objectives of state. This implies that economic foreign policy should be comprehensive, which means it should cover both economic relations with foreign countries and the internal economic relations of a given country. More so, it should be constructed to make the effects of the foreign policy felt far beyond the scope of activities of the entities directly involved in economic relations with foreign countries, affecting all economic entities and sectors, with only the scale of this influence being varying. Foreign policy should therefore stem from a comprehensive balance of its effects.

The environments within which foreign economic policy takes places are the domestic environment and the international or external environment. The external environment entails all the contingencies of the international system that affect and influence the economic goals and objectives of states. The domestic environment of foreign economic policy according to (Otubanjo 999) refers to the features, factors and forces peculiar to the state where foreign economic policy is being made or emanates from (Wanjohi, 2011). These features include the geographical location of the state, its peculiarity, natural and human resources, the nature of the political system, quality of leadership and the nature of economic interaction among groups in the society. This study agrees with (Adegboyega et al, 2007) that the domestic environment determines the role a nation plays in the international system. This is because domestic structures of foreign economic policy determine the amount of social effects which can be devoted to foreign economic policy (Kissinger, 1969). Therefore, these imply that foreign economic policy connotes an interaction of the domestic and foreign elements that affects the aspirations of the state whether positively or negatively. In other words, it is used to depict the driving factor behind Nigeria’s interaction with other nations of the world. It is summed as the declared intentions of a state. Foreign economic policy objectives concern the goal-values that a state aspires to attain in its external relations. Foreign economic policy objectives serve as guiding principles for a country as it relates with the international environment.

The analysis of states foreign economic policy has been at various levels basically three: the individual, the state and the systemic levels of analysis. Although majority of scholars uphold the state level of analysis as the most important, it is essential to note that states are mere empty entities without individuals (Goldstein & Pevehouse, 2007:15). Nothing changes without someone driving the course of change. At the state level, individuals make up interest groups, political organizations and governmental organizations and bureaucracies. The whole essence of the above statements is that the place of the individual trait of leaders cannot be overlooked in the analysis of foreign economic policy and a country’s national transformational agenda. The distinct personalities of leaders Nigeria has had have in

various ways influenced Nigeria's foreign economic policymaking it tend towards continuity and changes at different times in the course of our history.

According to Smith (1954) and Ricardo (1957); foreign economy policy can be divide into free trade policy and protectionist policy. Between these two extreme approaches, a number of intermediate solutions can exist, with a larger or smaller dose of liberalism and protectionism.

Free Trade Policy: A free trade policy has its root in the doctrine of economic liberalism in which market forces automatically ensure full utilization of all factors of production and economic equilibrium. Free trade is essentially making trade easier by allowing the market to balance needs, supply and demand with a nation. It is an agreement or pact between two or more nations to reduce barriers to import and export commodities between them (Landon, 1978). Under free trade policy, goods and services can be bought and sold across international borders with little or no government tariffs, quote, subsidies, or prohibitions to inhibit their exchange. This concept is the opposite of trade protectionism or economic isolationism. International marketers, corporate bodies, multinational organizations carryout their businesses with no or little government influence apart from policies on security to secure business environment. Traders import and export commodities at their won consideration base on market demand. Government provides free will to market without subsidy nor reduce tariffs slated for such transaction, free trade in the market system encourage competition, the forces of demand determine the supply while the market system control the price of commodities.

Protectionism Policy: A protectionist policy in international economic consists of the utilization by the state of means and instruments applied by foreign economic policy, macroeconomic policy to achieve their goods. Protectionism in foreign trade is a derivative of the policy of state to protect it's economy through series of intervention (Bozyk, 2006). Advocates of state interventionism believes that the assumptions of the classical free market and free trade theory are far from reality. According to proponents of this theory, Economic subjects are highly diversified in terms of size, competitiveness and technical land. A large number of market and monopolized which diminishes or even excludes competition under such conditions, a free market gives rise to the growth of pathological phenomena such as unjustified price rises, lack of interest in improving quality and modernity of output, also rising unemployment and inflation. Government control market system take into consideration the needs of it's population, regulate what to import, how to import, quantities and qualities of commodities. Nigeria government have several established institution to checkmate qualities and the particular commodities to import in order to ensure it's citizens buys are exposed to quality services. The Nigeria central bank control financial flow of individuals and corporate organization to ensure compliance to financial regulations, the Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON) check qualities of every commodities to maintain standard, NAFDAC is empowered to regulate activities of drugs and food related items for quality control. The government could at any time reduce of go tax holiday to subsidise a given needed product for the masses. Government also can intervene through exchange rate subsidy, by selling currency at official rate to reduce the cost goods and services.

Foreign Direct Investment

Dunning (1980) in this framework, opined that countries engage in foreign direct investment based on three important advantages: the first one is the Ownership advantages, second, Location advantages, and lastly the Internalization advantages (OLI) location advantages relate to the country-specific advantages that the firm gains when investing abroad. Internalization advantages relate to the production kind of activities undertaken by the firm itself rather than licensing them to another party. Ownership advantages may include firm's superiority over its competitors in terms of marketing practices or on the technological front (Alam & Shah, 2013). Krugman, et al. (2012) further argued that multinational corporations operating in a foreign country incur many costs including failure of knowledge about local market conditions, cultural, legal and other costs. Thus, foreign firms should have some advantages that can offset these costs. Ownership advantage is a firm-specific advantage as earlier stated, that gives power to firms over their competitors. Among other things are advantage in technology, management techniques, easy access to finance, economies of scale and capacity to coordinate activities. Location advantages are country-specific advantages. For foreign investors to fully reap the benefit of firm-specific advantages,

they usually consider the location advantages of the host country. This includes accessibility and low cost of natural resource and distance, adequate infrastructure, political atmosphere, macroeconomic conditions, and financial position of the host country which are components of country risk. Consequently, the location advantage of the host country is one essential factor that determines the foreign investors' decision. Internalization is multinational corporations' ability to internalize some activities that protect their exclusive right to tangible and intangible assets and defend their competitive advantage from rival firms. All these three conditions must be met before transnational companies open a subsidiary in a foreign country (Oluchukwu, 2013).

The study conceptualized foreign direct investment, to mean an investment in a foreign country where the investors retain control over the investment. According to (Aremu 2000), foreign direct investment shows that the owner of the money is coming to direct the affairs of investment, the owner has an effective voice in the management to control and direct the activities of his/her investment. FDI typically takes the form of a foreigner setting up a subsidiary or taking over/control of an existing firm in the country in question. Usman (2008) asserted that FDI involves the internationalization of product in order to service markets which were formally served by experts. Also, FDI is distinguished from other forms of foreign investment by the fact that it involves not only foreign investment ownership but also foreign control. In other words, FDI occurs only if an individual or organization in a foreign country gains sufficient interest in an operation to acquire control. Therefore, FDI as a concept differs from international or foreign investment which is a much wide concept.

Nexus between Foreign Economic Policy and Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

From the above analysis, we have observed with keen interest, the complex relationships between economic foreign policy and foreign direct investment as it affects Nigeria. It is evident that economic foreign policy, when conceived as the way a country relates with its external environment, has serious implications for the country's international image. In other words, foreign relations invariably dictate how foreigners are received and treated by host countries. It pave ways for foreign investment, determines the direction, location, activities and area of interest for foreign direct investment. The feed-back mechanism embedded in the foreign economic policy formulation and implementation process can help to drive foreign direct investment.

The critical linkage between foreign economic policy and foreign direct investment is focused to provide an illumination into how foreign economic policy, when carefully articulated can promote a country's economic development. Adelusi et al (2014) had argued that the linkage between foreign economic policy and foreign direct investment provides a specific context which identifies the extent to which specific issues can positively or negatively exert influence on achievement of a given policy. Foreign economic policy constitutes a force for positive international image, indeed, a force for positive change, which should be maximally harnessed for economic development. It therefore, suffices to mention that an engagement of a robust foreign economic policy position invariably promotes a country's economic development.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

President Goodluck Jonathan who took over the mantle of Nigeria's leadership from his predecessor, President UmaruMusa Yar'adua also undertook so many diplomatic visits to further launder the image of the country and diversify her foreign revenue sources. Just as his two predecessors, he effectively utilized Nigeria's foreign policy to attract foreign investors and other international business/development partners to do business in the country. Jonathan's tenure maintained the status-quo of sustaining the influx of more FDI into the country; but still with the tip tilting more in favour of Oil and Gas (O&G). There was however underperformance of the country's foreign policy where it failed to support its economic relations instrument for directing the attracted FDI towards boosting the industrial and manufacturing sector and subsector of the economy. These critical sectors and sub-sectors have the highest likelihood of expanding the country's foreign revenue sources through the manufacture of unique products and goods in which Nigeria has comparative advantage in the international market. It is this failure that motivate the study.

Onyeche (2023) studied on “Goodluck Jonathan’s foreign policy agenda: prioritizing Nigeria’s domestic progress and navigating international challenges” the study adopt qualitative research design, only secondary data we collected from textbooks, journals, newspaper, internet facilities etc, the study did not use theory, in his findings, it acknowledged that while foreign policy is often conceived as external facing, and for determining a country’s identity outside, the results are often in the form of domestic progress. For example, the Chinese “Belt and Road” initiative that seeks to invest in infrastructure in more than 150 countries, is in fact the construction of the infrastructure to facilitate the shipment of goods from China. Even the US, more often than not, its interference in global issues is often a play to protect cheap sources of energy for American businesses. The move by the Jonathan administration to focus on Nigeria’s domestic issues rather the Afro-centric focus of the country’s foreign policy up until then was not only justified, but it was also a necessity. Nigeria cannot aspire to lead Africa without first resolving its internal challenges. That the Buhari administration, which ran against and replaced the GEJ administration, continued to make Nigeria’s domestic issues the center piece of its foreign policy is a pointer that that was something the GEJ administration got right.

Olokoyo (2012) examined the effects of foreign direct investment (FDI) on the development of Nigerian economy. The paper tried to answer the question: what are the FDI determinants in Nigeria and how do they affect the Nigerian economy? The study employed the use of ordinary least square (OLS) regression technique to test the time series data from 1970-2007. The model used hypothesizes that there is a functional relationship between the economic development of Nigeria using the real gross domestic product (RGDP) and foreign direct investment. The regression analysis results evidently do not provide much support for the view of a robust link between FDI and economic growth in Nigeria as suggested by extant previous literatures. Though the result does not imply that FDI is unimportant, the model analysis reduces the confidence in the belief that FDI has exerted an independent growth effect in Nigeria.

Brecher (2013) gave an assessment of issues of interest in foreign economic policy in Nigeria, the paper answers certain research question: what are the factors prompted Nigeria foreign economic policy? What are the major components of Nigeria foreign economic policies? The study used qualitative research methodology, content analysis was adopted to analysed secondary data collected from various textbooks, journals, policy documents, internet material etc, he summed the components of major state interest as geography, external global environment, personalities, economic and military position and public opinion as the major components of economic foreign policy.

Eravwoke and Imide (2013) analyzed corruption, foreign direct investment and its impact on exchange rate of the Nigeria economy. The ultimate objective of this study centers on an empirical investigation of the impact of corruption, foreign direct investment and its impact on exchange rate of the Nigerian economy. In order to achieve these objectives the study used the ordinary least squares regression analyses, augmented dickey fuller unit root test and the co-integration test. The unit root test revealed that all the variables were stationary at first difference and the short run result revealed that corruption is very high in Nigeria and that have help to depreciate the currency of the country with regards its exchange to other currencies.

Ajayi, Anifowose, and Ekwere (2023) undergone an Empirical Analysis of Foreign Direct Investment and Economic Growth in Nigeria” the paper investigates the effect of foreign direct investment on the Nigerian economy with particular emphasis on export growth rate, trade openness, external debt growth rate, foreign portfolio investment, exchange rate and inflation from 1985-2020. Data for the study were obtained from the World Bank Digest of Statistics and Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The study employed regression analysis of the ordinary least square approach in analyzing the data for the study. Major findings from the investigation demonstrate that the export growth rate, trade openness, external debt growth rate, foreign portfolio investment and inflation rate have no significant effect on the Nigerian economy, while exchange rate has a significant effect on the Nigerian economy. The paper therefore suggested that government should embrace export-led growth strategies on long-term development plans. There is also the need for Nigerian government to make favourable trade policies and investment conditions friendlier to boost the inflow of foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Theories are formulated to explain, interpret and understand phenomena and in many areas extend existing knowledge within the limits of critical bounding assumption. It involves relating the problem under study to the assumption, postulations, and the principles of a particular theory employed. Therefore, the study adopted dependency theory to help explain the research work. The theory came as a criticism of modernization theory, which was falling increasingly out of favor because of continued widespread poverty in much of the world. At that time the assumptions of liberal theories of development were under attack. It was used to explain the causes of over urbanization, a theory that urbanization rates outpaced industrial growth in several developing countries. Dependency theory, is a theoretical approach of understanding economic underdevelopment that emphasizes the economic standard constraints imposed by the global economic order (James, 1985). The theory was proposed in the late 1950s by the Argentine economist and statesman Raúl Prebisch. Dependency theory postulate that underdevelopment is mainly caused by the peripheral position of affected countries in the world economy Prebisch observed that the term of trade for underdeveloped countries relative to the developed countries had deteriorated over time: the underdeveloped countries were able to purchase fewer and fewer manufactured goods from the developed countries in exchange for a given quantity of their raw materials exports. Typically, underdeveloped countries offer cheap labour and raw materials on the world market, these resources are sold to advanced economies, which have the means to transform them into finished goods (Rodney,1972). The underdeveloped nations mostly Nigeria and other African countries must employ some degree of protectionism in trade if they were to enter a self-sustaining development path, especially at import-substitution industrialisation (ISI), not a trade-and-export orientation, was the best strategy for underdeveloped countries. Underdeveloped countries like Nigeria and other African nations end up purchasing the finished products at high prices, depleting the capital they might otherwise devote to upgrading their own productive capacity. John, Bruc & Williamson (2003). The result is a vicious cycle that perpetuates the division of the world economy between a rich core and a poor periphery. While moderate dependency theorists, such as (Cardoso 2003) considered some level of development to be possible within this system, more-radical scholars, such as the German American economic historian Andre Gunder Frank, argued that the only way out of dependency was the creation of a noncapitalist (socialist) national economy (Olanike, 2012).

The theory remains relevant in explaining economic and power relations between states in the twenty-first century globalised economy. The manifestation of the unequal and exploitative relationships between the Global North and Global South countries can be seen in many spheres, including economic, political, military, and ideology. Although many nations have been affected by both the positive and negative effects of the dependency theory. The idea of national dependency on another nation is not a relatively new concept developing countries in Africa and Nigeria in particular has falling a victim of depending on technological transfer from advanced industrilised nation and importation of other commodities to boost it's economy. Dependency is perpetuated by using capitalism and finance. The dependent nations come to owe the developed nations so much money and capital that it is not possible to escape the debt, continuing the dependency for the foreseeable future (Arno, 2003).

The dependency theory can be used to explain Nigeria's reliance on foreign aid from the IMF. The motive behind aid issuance aligns with the dependency theory assumption of a polarised world between the 'Centre' and 'Periphery'. Nigeria's extreme dependence on loans from the IMF has worsened its debt crisis as it has resulted in a debt burden that has distorted the country's development. Due to the resources directed toward debt servicing, the debt crisis has restricted the country's capacity to invest in critical growth-sustaining infrastructure (Yusuf & Mohd, 2021). Consequently, Nigeria has found itself in a very "tightrope debt trap" with unsustainable external debt. From the dependency theory's perspective, the IMF's loans can be seen as a mechanism used by highly industrialised nations to maintain the dependence of the Periphery on their economies under the pretense of assisting in achieving economic development.

METHODOLOGY

This research is basically qualitative and non-experimental; therefore, it is based on the single case ex post facto design. An ex post facto design is used when experimental research is not possible, such as when people have self-selected levels of an independent variable or when a treatment is naturally occurring and the researcher could not "control" the degree of its use. research design is very relevant to our study given the nature of the phenomenon under investigation. This design is useful when using human subjects in real-world situations and when a treatment is naturally occurring and the researcher could not "control" the degree of its use. In applying the single case *ex post facto* design to our study, the test of the hypothesis involves observing the independent variable (Goodluck Jonathan's foreign policy) and dependent variable (inflow of Foreign Direct Investment into Nigeria between 2010 and 2015) at the same time because the effects of the former on the latter have already taken place before this investigation. It also involves observing the standard of living of Nigerian citizens prior to the attraction of FDI through Goodluck Jonathan's foreign economic policy and what it was after the attraction of the FDI to see how the former impacted on the latter.

The study adopted a secondary method of data collection, while our sources were based mainly on secondary sources of data collection, which are published and unpublished materials such as relevant textbooks, journal articles, conferences papers, government publications, magazines, newspapers, policy statement, and online materials on foreign economic policy and foreign direct investments in Nigeria. The data for this study were analyzed using qualitative, descriptive analysis. This involves logically breaking down the data collected to draw inferences about the relationship between the variables that are of interest to the researcher on the particular occasion. It also implies that data collection naturally leads up to data analysis such that in the course of the analysis the collected data is broken and given appropriate treatment so as to read meaning out of the data that has been generated, presented, tested and interpreted.

IMPACT OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC POLICY OF GOODLUCK JONATHAN

President Goodluck Jonathan, upon his ascension to power, constituted a Presidential Advisory Council on Foreign Affairs headed by Chief Emeka Anyaoku to review Nigeria's foreign economic policy. At the end of this brain storming session, Nigeria's foreign economic policy shifted from Africa as the centre of her foreign policy to an investment and export driven foreign policy. His administration adopted a policy that is intricately tied to Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). This foreign economic policy was termed "economic diplomacy", and is believed to be an extension of Nigeria's domestic policy to alleviate poverty, create jobs and diversify the economy. In the words of the Foreign Affairs Minister, Ambassador Olugbenga Ashiru, "Nigeria's foreign economic policy would now be investment driven, defining a new driving force as different from the previous focus on Africa". Punch Newspaper: (2011, 3). According to Ashiru (2011) "the emphasis of Nigeria's Foreign Economic Policy is on investments. The investment will have multiplier effects on the economy in terms of creating jobs and the overall growth of the economy. While we retain the leadership role in the sub-region and play a leading role in the continent, the foreign policy direction will be used to propel economic development of our country. All our Embassies and High Commissions especially in Asia, Europe and America will now promote investments (Omoh, 2011). The principle of reciprocity is also a feature of the indicated policy. The Jonathan government adopted reciprocity in both its positive and negative aspects, proposing that where countries unnecessarily delay or deny Nigerians visa applications without just cause, the Nigerian consulate will retaliate, and where visa applicants are attended to without being subjected to indignities, Nigeria will return the favour. Also, where Nigerians are being maltreated, citizens of defaulting countries will bear the brunt, as in the case of deportations between Nigeria and South Africa in 2012. (Jaji & Ayotunde: 2016). The Jonathan's administration noted that Nigeria will not abandon the responsibility of protecting her citizens abroad, charging the Nigerian Embassies and High Commissions to care for Nigerians living in the diaspora.

Akinterinwa (2014) pointed out four techniques employed by the Jonathan administration in pursuance of his economic foreign policy, viz:

- (1) Overhaul of the Foreign Service aimed at ensuring expertise and experience in Nigeria's foreign missions.
- (2) Partnership with specialized institutions and government bodies so as to strengthen the foundation on which foreign policies are formed and to aid in achieving the overall objective of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs.
- (3) Strategic Partnerships with countries which Nigeria has trade relations, marketing indigenous goods and encouraging other economies to invest in the various industries.
- (4) Collaboration with the Organized Private Sector(OPS) where the business class and the government rubbed minds after the budget, and the opinions of the former group were taken into consideration in policy making.

The final and major strategy employed by the Jonathan administration to ensure success of economic diplomacy is called the Transformation Agenda. This Agenda is a comprehensive initiative launched to address Nigeria's economic underdevelopment, as well as review the role of the legislature and the judiciary within a period of four years (2011 – 2015) (Benjamin 2012); Chaired by President Jonathan himself, and coordinated by the Minister of Finance, Dr. Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala, the Transformation Agenda covers the following key sectors: "job creation, education, health, power, transportation, Niger Delta, labour and productivity, foreign policy and economic diplomacy, legislature, governance, judiciary and justice delivery, public expenditure management, and information and communication and technology (ICT)" (Gyong, 2012).

According to Lawal (2015), data analysis informs that manufacturing's contribution declined to 38.6 per cent in the 1990s and further to 29.4 per cent during the 21st Century: 2000. The contribution of Nigeria's manufacturing sector was on average below 5.0 per cent in the last two decades. It is important to enhance understanding of this title by clarifying that the relatively high contribution of oil sector to the industrial sector contribution has resulted largely from crude production contrasted to the associated 'core industrial' components of that sub-sector such as refining and petrochemicals. While the contribution of wholesale and retail trade and services has more or less remained stable during the study period the contribution of building increased steadily: from 5.3 per cent in the 1990s to 8.3 per cent in the 2000s, but declined consistently, afterwards, to 1.8 per cent during 2009-2014. The foreign direct investment has increased in the past twenty years to become the most common type of capital flow. The most important economic reason for attracting FDI at the beginning of the transformation process of an economy was to facilitate the privatization and restructuring of the economy key sectors (Heimann, 2013). The privatization and reconstruction process nearly comes to an end, the main reason to pursue foreign direct investment in major sectors of the economy is to enhance productivity or output, encourage employment, stimulate innovation and technology transfer as well as enhance sustained manufacturing output growth as witnessed in most developing nations of the world like Nigeria. The pattern of the FDI that does exist is often skewed towards extractive industries, meaning that the differential rate of FDI inflow into Sub-Saharan African countries like Nigeria has been adduced to be due to natural resources, although the size of the local market may also be a consideration (Asiedu, 2013). Nigeria as a country, given her natural resource base and large market size, qualifies to be a major recipient of FDI in Africa and indeed is one of the top three leading African countries that consistently received FDI in the past decade. However, the level of FDI attracted by Nigeria is mediocre compared with the resource base and potential need (Asiedu, 2013).

Impact of Jonathan's Foreign Economic Diplomacy

The appointment of Okonjo-Iweala, a reputable Economist, clearly illustrated the main thrust of the Jonathan's Transformation Agenda, the administration did not record much in the way of success of the lofty aims of the agenda. Internal challenges constituted more of a problem to sustaining the vision of the administration's adopted foreign policy. The purpose of the transformation agenda was rendered useless with the problems of poor governance and mismanagement of funds. Corruption in the public service is also a major contributing factor. Femi Otedola, a member of the Economic Management Team was involved in a bribery scandal. In the area of trade and commerce facilitation by diplomats and ambassadors, as pointed out by Babayo (2014), Nigerian diplomats were ill-equipped for the new role

that was assigned to them. They were still largely generalists. The involvement of Nigerian diplomats in international economic relations was peripheral, it consisted largely of attending meetings with so-called experts from the home Ministries of Finance, Planning, and Trade that had primary responsibility for Nigeria's external economic and commercial relations. All these reflect very negatively on the administration and its transformation agenda as a whole. Undoubtedly, President Jonathan scored some positive points.

However, on the whole, Jaji and Ayotunde (2016) posited that the foreign policy techniques employed under Jonathan's administration have not in any monumental way made the country better off than it was. Foreign Direct Investment into Nigeria in 2011, when President Jonathan took office, increased from \$6.5 billion in the previous year to \$8.9 billion (Umejie, 2014). However, the figure has since been plummeting. In 2012 and 2013, FDI was \$7 billion and \$5.5 billion respectively (Umejie, 2014). The administration observed that "lack of continuity, consistency and commitment (3Cs) to agreed policies, programmes and projects..." is the reason why growth and development of the Nigerian economy does not correspond with "the overall welfare of Nigerian citizens, rising unemployment, inequality and poverty"(Akinterinwa, 2014). Akinterinwa stressed further that:

"The administration had not changed its policies between 2011 and 2014, but perhaps its level of commitment had diminished, and it was not consistent in its efforts. Contributing to the decline of investments is the situation of insecurity in the country. Attempts to mobilize the diaspora community to either return to Nigeria or make investments in the economy have come to naught. The prevalence of unemployment, corruption and insecurity was discouraging. Expatriates were unconvinced that Nigeria had anything to offer them."

Jonathan's Foreign economic policy also continued the Citizen Diplomacy of Late President Yar' Adua. He noted that his administration will not abandon the responsibility of protecting Nigerian citizens abroad, charging the Nigerian Embassies and High Commissions to care for Nigerians living in other countries. In the words of Ashiru in (Atoyebi, 2012): "past policy thrust is fair and decent treatment wherever they may be. We will continue to insist that Nigeria be accorded respect and treated with dignity. Our charge to the Ambassadors and High Commissioners is that the welfare of Nigerians in Diaspora must be taken seriously. However, as we strive to protect and promote the interests of our compatriots abroad, we also reiterate to them the imperative to be law abiding in their places of abode" (Atoyebi, 2012):

Jonathan's administration also advocated for Preventive Diplomacy as a means of conflict prevention. While addressing the United Nations Security Council in 2011, Jonathan said that "Nigeria viewed conflict prevention as a subject. Indeed, Nigeria has invested resources to support the campaign for Preventive Diplomacy especially within our sub region. We have adopted the use of Preventive Diplomacy in addressing complex questions arising from armed conflicts" (Onuorah & Obiagwu, 2011). Here's an analysis of key aspects of his economic foreign policy:

Economic Diversification

Agriculture: One of the focal points of Jonathan's foreign economic policy was the agricultural sector. The administration sought to reduce Nigeria's heavy reliance on oil revenues by promoting agriculture as a key driver of economic growth, this included initiatives to attract foreign investment in agribusiness and improve food security. The Growth Enhancement Support Scheme (GES) was introduced to provide subsidies and incentives to farmers.

Manufacturing: Efforts were made to promote industrialization and increase local production in sectors such as automobile manufacturing, cement production, and textiles. However, the success of these initiatives was mixed, and the country continued to face challenges related to infrastructure and regulatory environment.

Foreign Investment Promotion

China: Jonathan's administration actively courted Chinese investment. Nigeria received significant loans and infrastructure investments from China, particularly in sectors such as railways, telecommunications, and energy. The China-Nigeria relationship was crucial in financing large-scale infrastructure projects.

Diaspora Engagement: The administration also encouraged Nigerian Diaspora communities to invest in the country through initiatives like the Nigerian Diaspora Direct Investment Summit. The hope was to tap into the financial resources and expertise of Nigerians living abroad.

Trade Relations:

Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS): Nigeria continued to play a central role within ECOWAS to promote regional economic integration and trade. Efforts were made to reduce trade barriers within the region and facilitate cross-border trade.

African Union and Regional Trade Agreements: Nigeria supported efforts to create a single market within the African Union and participated in regional trade agreements such as the West African Economic and Monetary Union (WAEMU) and the Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs).

Oil and Energy Diplomacy:

Oil Diplomacy: Given Nigeria's status as a major oil producer, Jonathan's government sought to strengthen relations with oil-consuming countries, including the United States, China, and India. These countries were important partners in Nigeria's oil exports, and discussions often centered on energy security and pricing.

Gas Export: The administration explored opportunities to increase Nigeria's natural gas exports and develop the liquefied natural gas (LNG) sector. Gas diplomacy aimed to diversify revenue sources away from oil.

Infrastructure Development:

Transportation and Energy: Infrastructure development was a key element of economic foreign policy. Major projects such as the rehabilitation of railways and construction of new roads aimed to improve transportation and energy distribution, which were seen as critical for economic growth and foreign investment.

Impact of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) Inflow on Domestic Industrial Capacity in Nigeria

We tested the second hypothesis of this study which states that the how did inflow of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) under Goodluck Jonathan administration impeded domestic industrial capacity in Nigeria. To do this, we shall examine the volume of FDI inflow into Nigeria during the period under study, the percentage of the FDI inflow into the industrial sector and the impact of the inflow in industrial production measured in terms of industrial production exports as well as import of manufactured goods.

UNCTAD's World Investment Report 2004 reported that Africa's outlook for FDI is promising but that the expected surge was yet to manifest. FDI is still concentrated in only a few countries for many reasons, ranging from negative image of the region, to poor infrastructure, corruption and foreign exchange shortages, an unfriendly macroeconomic policy environment, among others. Nigeria's share of FDI inflow to Africa averaged around 10%, from 24.19% in 1990 to a low level of 5.88% in 2001 up to 11.65% in 2002. UNCTAD (2003) showed Nigeria as the continent's second top FDI recipient after Angola in 2001 and 2002. Nigeria has since overtaken Angola as the continent's investment destination of choice. For instance, UNCTAD recorded in its World Investment Report 2013, titled: "Global Value Chains: Investment and Trade for Development," that FDI inflows to Nigeria stood at \$7.03 billion. South Africa recorded \$4.572 billion, Ghana (\$3.295 billion), Egypt (\$2.798 billion), and Angola (-6.898 billion), among others.

A breakdown of the Global FDI report showed that Foreign Direct Investment flows to African countries increased by five per cent to \$50 billion in 2012, even as global FDI fell by 18 per cent. According to the report, global FDI fell by 18 per cent to \$1.35 trillion, while FDI was expected to increase to \$1.45 trillion in 2013, \$1.6 trillion in 2014 and \$1.8 trillion in 2015. UNCTAD said: "The road to FDI recovery is thus proving bumpy and may take longer than expected. UNCTAD forecasts FDI in 2013 to remain close to the 2012 level, with an upper range of \$1.45 trillion – a level comparable to the pre-crisis average of 2005 to 2007." "Developing countries take the lead in 2012 – for the first time ever – developing economies absorbed more FDI than developed countries, accounting for 52 per cent of global FDI flows. This is

partly because the biggest fall in FDI inflows occurred in developed countries, which now account for only 42 per cent of global flows.”

In 2011, Nigeria was ranked Africa’s biggest destination FDI, with total FDI inflows of \$8.92 billion. South Africa was ranked next with total FDI inflows of \$5.81 billion, while other African countries such as Ghana received \$3.22 billion; Congo, \$2.93 billion; and Algeria, \$2.57 billion worth of FDIs respectively. Experts argued that the FDI trend had been encouraging, though Nigeria needed to continue to address its security and political challenges to improve on the trend. Only last Tuesday, President Goodluck Jonathan inaugurated the General Electric’s \$1billion service and manufacturing facility in Calabar.

The ground breaking ceremony followed the Memorandum of Understanding signed by the Minister of Industry, Trade and Investment, Mr. Olusegun Aganga; and the Global Chairman/Chief Executive Officer of GE, Mr. Jeff Emmelt, in January. Procter & Gamble has also commenced a \$250million investment in Nigeria. The ground breaking for investment in Agbara Ogun state was held in July 2012.

Figure 1: Nigeria’s Net foreign direct investment inflow (US\$ billion)

Source: Statista Foreign Direct Investment Database online extracted (December 2023)

The details of FDI inflow into Nigeria for the period 2010 to 2015 are shown in figure 1. The nominal FDI inflow ranged from N6.03billion in 2010 to N3.06billion in 2015. Nigerian governments have viewed FDI as a vehicle for political and economic domination, the thrust of government’s policy through the Nigeria Enterprise Promotion Decree (NEPD) (indigenization policy) was to regulate rather than promote FDI. The NEPD was promulgated in 1972 to limit foreign equity participation in manufacturing and commercial sectors to a maximum of 60%. In 1977 a second indigenization decree was promulgated to further limit foreign equity participation in Nigeria business to 40%. Hence, between 1972 and 1995 official policy toward FDI was restrictive. The regulatory environment discouraged foreign participation resulting in an average flow of only 0.79% of GDP from 1973 to 1988.

The adoption of the structural adjustment programme in 1986 initiated the process of termination of the hostile policies towards FDI. A new industrial policy was introduced in 1989 with the debt to equity

conversion scheme as a component of portfolio investment. The Industrial Development Coordinating Committee (IDCC) was established in 1988 as a one-step agency for facilitating and attracting foreign investment flow. This was followed in 1995 by the repeal of the Nigeria Enterprises Promotion Decree and its replacement with the Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission Decree 16 of 1995. The NIPC absorbed and replaced the IDCC and provided for a foreign investor to set up a business in Nigerian with 100% ownership. Upon provision of relevant documents, NIPC will approve the application within 14 days (as opposed to four weeks under IDCC) or advise the applicant otherwise. Furthermore, in consonance with the NIPC decree, the Foreign Exchange (Monitoring and Miscellaneous Provision) Decree 17 of 1995 was promulgated to enable foreigners to invest in enterprise in Nigeria or in money market instruments with foreign capital that is legally brought into the country. The decree permits free regulation of dividends accruing from such investment or of capital in event of sale or liquidation. An export processing zone (EPZ) scheme adopted in 1999 allows interested persons to set up industries and businesses within demarcated zones, particularly with the objective of exporting the goods and services manufactured or produced within the zone.

In summary, the policies embarked on by the Nigerian government to attract foreign investors as a result of the introduction of the SAP could be categorized into five: the establishment of the Industrial Development Coordinating Committee (IDCC), investment incentive strategy, non-oil export stimulation and expansion, the privatization and commercialization programme, and the shift in macroeconomic management in favour of industrialization, deregulation and market-based arrangements.

Following the vigorous drive for the attraction of FDI by the Goodluck Jonathan administration, it has been reported that the administration attracted a modest inflow of FDI while it lasted. It has however been suggested that most FDI inflows into Nigeria are reinvested earnings from the oil multinationals (Kolawole & Henry, 2019). According to him, reinvested earnings have averaged two-thirds of overall FDI inflows in recent years, with the bulk directed towards the energy sector. There has been a modest surge in non-oil sector foreign investment in Nigeria in recent years, after it became clear that the previous regime of Olusegun Obasanjo, was firmly established and that economic growth was picking up. Although much of the investment was by large multinational companies that were already operating in the country, there have been some new European entrants since the beginning of this decade, and South African companies have also strongly increased their presence in recent years, particularly in the mobile phone sector. Nigeria the second largest FDI recipient has more of it concentrated in the extractive industry but a veritable non-oil sector, manufacturing sector that recorded 47% of FDI stock in 1992 has been a great source of FDI to the country. The recent banking consolidation exercise also boosted FDI (and portfolio inflows) into Nigeria as existing foreign banks increased the capitalization of their subsidiaries to meet the new minimum capital requirements.

Steinbock (2013) further noted that with its natural resources, size and growth, Nigeria is Africa's largest recipient of foreign investment. He however queried whether the huge FDI flows benefiting ordinary Nigerians? According to him, Global FDI is no longer immune to the post-global recession challenges. Last year, it plunged by a whopping 18 percent. Nonetheless, FDI inflows to African countries actually rose by five percent, to \$50 billion, while Nigeria receives the largest amount of FDI in Africa – almost 15 percent of the total. What about the Nigerians? Nigeria was ranked Africa's number one destination for foreign direct investment (FDI), for the second time in two years. The country's FDI inflows exceeded \$7 billion. In the post-global crisis years, FDI stock in Nigeria as a percentage of GDP has increased to 27.6 percent. In 2012, FDI flows in Nigeria as a percentage of gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) were almost 24 percent (Gyong, 2012). Under the 1995 Nigerian Investment Promotion Commission Act, 100 percent foreign ownership is allowed in all industries except for oil and gas. Typically, Nigeria's most important sources of FDI have been the home countries of the oil majors: the United States (Chevron Texaco, Exxon Mobil), the UK (Shell), China, and South Africa. Understandably, the government would like to bring in even more investment to meet its target of becoming one of the world's top-20 economies by 2020. The objective, however, is predicated on a sophisticated business environment, lower corruption and rising competitiveness.

Competitive Challenges: Usually, investors rely on global indicators to review FDI opportunities, focusing on business environment, corruption, and competitiveness. After some deterioration in the rankings over recent years, Nigeria moved up to 115th last year, thanks to improved macroeconomic conditions and a financial sector that is recovering from its 2009 crisis. The negatives include the institutional environment, e.g., concerns about the protection of property rights, ethics and corruption, undue influence, and government inefficiencies, as well as security. The country also receives poor assessments for infrastructure, health and primary education levels, and the low rates of ICT penetration. In the Doing Business Indicators (World Bank), Nigeria is ranked 131st. This performance is relatively weakest in such areas as starting a business, getting electricity, registering property, paying taxes, trading across borders, or resolving insolvency. Finally, Nigeria ranks 139th in the Corruption Perceptions, (Transparency International), far behind South Africa, Tanzania, Ethiopia and Sierra Leone. In this regard, perceived corruption is similar to that in Pakistan (139) and Bangladesh (144). According to him, in order to move higher in the value-added chain, Nigeria must improve its performance in these rankings. The country needs urgently to develop medium-term public-private partnerships to upgrade its business environment, fight corruption, and foster competitiveness.

Spreading Prosperity: This is the paradox: unlike those nations that attract FDI because of their relatively strong performance in competitiveness, their business environment, or their minimal corruption, Nigeria garners FDI despite its vulnerabilities. The bad news is that, in such a situation, the gains of natural resources are unlikely to benefit the nation as a whole. Rather, the status quo virtually ensures that small enclaves in the economy will grow richer, even as the real per capita income of the majority remains relatively low. That's a risky recipe to economic polarization and social division. What Nigeria needs is to attract investors primarily with higher productivity. The goal should be to improve the quality of the location in ways that benefit many companies and industries, not just one or two companies. Third, the point should be to develop 'sticky' incentives that are tied to the location rather than the investor. Moreover, the focus should be on sustained investment rather than transient one-time deals. From the standpoint of competitiveness, oil-driven FDI is a distraction because it steers attention away from the fundamentals of competitiveness.

FDI that Benefits the Nation: President Goodluck Jonathan said the economy could achieve a 7.2% growth rate before the year-end. In a grim international environment, such growth will attract investor interest worldwide. However, broader industrialization could achieve greater spread effects across the economy. Global FDI is no longer unaffected by the gloomy and uncertain environment, including the potentially longer growth slowdown in several emerging economies – especially if the anticipated unwinding of monetary policy stimulus in the U.S. leads to sustained capital flow reversals. Since, however, Nigeria's FDI relies on its natural resources, it is likely to remain relatively immune from the decline of overall global FDI. Nigeria's challenge is to translate a lucrative enclave of the economy into national gains, through increased competitiveness, enhanced business environment and lower corruption. That's a tall order. However, it is vital to avoid deepening economic polarization and rising social pressures over time. With respect to the inflow of FDI into the export sector of Nigeria's economy, a study by Oyatoye et al (2011) noted that empirical work on the linkages between Direct Foreign Investment and Export has not tried to establish causation, that is, to determine for example, whether inflows of Direct Foreign Investment cause export to be greater than what should be expected or whether expanding exports attract increased Direct Foreign Investment. The focus rather has been on the more modest goal of seeking to determine whether increase in Direct Foreign Investment (DFI) will increase export or vice versa.

Figure 2: FDI Inflows, Global and by Group of Economies, 1995–2014 (Billions of Dollars)

Source: UNCTAD, FDI/MNE database (www.unctad.org/fdistatistics)

From the table above global foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows fell by 16 per cent in 2014 to \$1.23 trillion, down from \$1.47 trillion in 2013 (figure 1). This is mostly explained by the fragility of the global economy, policy uncertainty for investors and elevated geopolitical risks. New investments were also offset by some large divestments. The decline in FDI flows was in contrast to macroeconomic variables such as GDP, trade, gross fixed capital formation and employment, which all grew. Although the outlook for FDI remains uncertain, an upturn in FDI flows occurred in 2015. Strengthening economic growth in developed economies, the demand-stimulating effects of lower oil prices and accommodating monetary policy, and continued investment liberalization and promotion measures could favourably affect FDI flows. Both UNCTAD's FDI forecast model and its business survey of large MNEs show a rise of FDI flows in and after 2015. Global FDI inflows grew by 11 per cent to \$1.4 trillion in 2015. Flows increased further to \$1.5 trillion and \$1.7 trillion in 2016 and 2017, respectively. The share of MNEs increase FDI expenditures over the years 2015 to 2017 rose from 24 to 32 per cent, according to UNCTAD's business survey. Data for the first few months of 2015 are consistent with this forecast. However, a number of economic and political risks, including ongoing uncertainties in the Eurozone, potential spillovers from geopolitical tensions and persistent vulnerabilities in emerging economies, disrupted the projected recovery.

CONCLUSION

This study employed secondary data to critically examine the effect of foreign economic policy on foreign direct investment under President Goodluck Jonathan Administration (2011-2015). It reviewed various related theories and literature to analyze and explain the nexus between foreign policy and FDI in Nigeria. The country recorded several inefficiencies in the foreign economic policy even though its Foreign Direct Investment hits 4.69 billion USD in 2014, largest economy in Africa after 2014 rebase as well as the recognition by UNCTAD; Nigeria as the best place for foreign investors in Africa in 2014. Even in the face of these developments, we still recorded negative effects on domestic economic activities, the poverty rate in Nigeria was still high with high rate of inflation, despite recent improved growth performance of the Nigerian economy, key economic indicators revealed that industrial development in Nigeria is on the decline rather than improving. It noted that crude oil export with little local value addition followed by agriculture and services have been the main drivers of growth with the result that economic growth in Nigeria has not promoted desired structural changes that would make

manufacturing the engine of growth, thereby create employment, and promote technological innovations and development.

It was further observed that as a consequence composite employment data showed that the rate of unemployment surged to 19.7% at end-December 2014 from 14.6% in 2010 and by January 2015, the unemployment rate was 21.1%. Between 2010 and 2015, more than 850 manufacturing companies either shut down or temporarily halted production. Capacity utilization in manufacturing was around 53% on average. Imports of manufactured goods dwarf sales of homegrown products – manufactured goods have constituted the biggest category of imports since the 1980s. Nigeria spends about \$8 million dollars per day importing food. It noted further that the biggest problem facing rapid industrialization in the country over the past decade has been inadequate infrastructure in general and lack of power supply in particular. On the strength of our findings therefore, the study concludes that the foreign economic policy of the Goodluck Jonathan administration did play a role in FDI inflow. While which enabled the delisting of Nigeria from the discriminatory rule of the Department of Homeland Security on special screening of passengers on international flights to the United States that specifically targeted Nigerians (consequent upon the Christmas day attempted bombing a US airline by a Nigerian Abdu Mutallab, with respect to the drive for FDI, it has rightly been noted that though the administration recorded appreciable inflow of FDI, such inflows were rarely targeted at the industrial productive sector, which constitutes the driving force of modern economies and as a result, failed to aid the development of the domestic industrial capacity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Following from the findings, the study recommends that:

- i. The federal government of Nigeria should work assiduously to strengthen the country's foreign economic policy in-line with the country's pressed economic needs of productive ventures that would stimulate economic development rather than continue to depend on illusive foreign inputs for her development needs.
- ii. The government should further check the actual implementation of foreign economic policy agenda to ensure the basic objective of foreign direct investment is achieved, FDI implementation should look at domestic interest of economy like agriculture, infrastructure, industries etc.
- iii. Rather than depend and canvass for foreign direct investment which is usually attracted at concessionary terms, the government should invest more in the provision of infrastructural facilities to boost domestic economic activities that would create the right economic environment attractive to foreign capital investment without having to depend that may not have impact on domestic productivity.

REFERENCES

- Ade-Ibijola, A. O. (2013) "Overview of National Interest, Continuities and Flaws in Nigeria Foreign Policy" *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences* January 2013, Vol. 3, No. 1 ISSN: 2222-6990 565 www.hrmars.com/journals
- Adeniran, T. (2007): *Introduction to International Relations*. Yaba: Macmillan .
- Ashiru, O. (2011). Nigeria's foreign policy: New realities in a changing world. Being paper presented at a luncheon organised by the Association of Retired Ambassadors of Nigeria, April 16.
- Asobie, H. A. (1991) "Nigeria: Economic Diplomacy and National Interest – An Analysis of the Politics of Nigeria's External Economic Relations" *Nigerian Journal of International Affairs*, Vol. 17 No 2.
- Benjamin C. O. (2012); Nigeria's transformation agenda: The Management and Leadership Challenges: Nigerian Institute of Management (Chartered).
- Chidozie, F., Ibieta, J., & Ujara, E. (2014). Foreign Policy, International Image And National Transformation: A Historical Perspective. *International Journal Of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 2(4), 49-58
- Collier, P. (2008). *The bottom billion: Why poorest countries are failing and what can be done about it*. Oxford University Press, 17 and 20.

- Collier, P., & Hoeffler, A. (2014). On the incidence of civil war in Africa. *The Journal of Conflict Resolutions*, 46(1), 13-28.
- Gyong, J. E. (2012). "A Social Analysis of the Transformation Agenda of President Goodluck Heywood, A. (2007). *Politics*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Lawal, L., (2015); Developmental diplomacy in a globalised world: The leadership question: Central Bank of Nigeria, 19th October 2012.
- Leege, D.C. & Francis, W.L. (1974). *Political Research: Design, Measurement and Analysis*, Macmillan
- Okolie, A. (2009). Fundamental Issues in Foreign Policy Making and Implementation In Nigeria." In A. Okolie (Ed.), *Contemporary Readings on Nigeria's External Relations: Issues, Perspectives And Challenges* (3-19). Ebonyi: Willyrose and Appleseed Publishing Coy.
- Olokoyo (2012) examined the effects of foreign direct investment (FDI) on the development of Nigerian economy.
- Onyeche, E. (2023). Goodluck Jonathan foreign policy agenda: Prioritizing Nigeria's domestic progress and navigating international challenges. University of Birmingham <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372909360>
- Steinbock, Dan (2013) "Nigeria's huge FDI flow: Is this benefitting Nigerians?" August 19, <http://businessdayonline.com/2013/08/nigerias-huge-fdi-flow-is-this-benefitning-nigerians/> accessed 03.10.13
- Yusuf, A., & Mohd, S. (2021). The impact of government debt on economic growth in Nigeria. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 9(1), 1946249.